

A Proposed Security Algorithm for Securing IoT Data

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Abstract—Recently, the Internet-of-Things (IoT) provides new challenges to security and privacy. Security of IoT systems is considered a milestone. It is used in many appliances such as healthcare, e-voting, and industrial applications. Cryptography and steganography are applied to prevent attackers from reading secret data, where steganography is found to be best suited for applications that prevent attackers from knowing someone is sending secret data. Sending encrypted messages over the IoT channels reveals the existence of a sensitive data. When sensitive data is sent, the attackers can apply Denial-of-Service (DoS) attack. By using steganography on the same IoT channel, it will protect this data from DoS attack. This paper aims to propose a new steganography algorithm. This algorithm consists of four main steps: compression, encryption, splitting and hiding. After the first two steps, we split the data into 3 bytes and then hide these 3 bytes by choosing words with a number of characters same as the 3 bytes and then hide them using an automated dictionary that is shared between sender and receiver. The proposed algorithm is tested for different security attacks which it passed effectively. In addition, we had conducted a comparative study to briefly survey the new features which are added to the algorithm compared to other algorithms. The proposed algorithm was built in an IoT application. It took 10ms for coding and 13ms for decoding at the cloud, message size is 265 bits. Then, the experiment was used to evaluate the performance of the proposed algorithm.

Keywords — *Steganography, Cryptography, IoT, AES, IoT application.*

I. INTRODUCTION

IoT is a collection of a set of several interconnected services, objects, people and devices that are able to communicate, exchange information and data to fulfill a common goal in several applications and areas. IoT has many fields of implementation such as the agriculture, transportation, production, health and distribution of energy [1].

Data protection and privacy is one of the main IoT challenges [2]. The lack of safety measures would lead to decreased adoption by users and is thus one of the motivating

forces for the success of the IoT. IoT technologies provide many benefits in the smart cities, smart transportation, smart homes and infrastructure etc... [3,4]. However, the successful development and use of IoT-based services requires security and privacy. IoT security has always remained a critical point of concern, since the very dawn of IoT, there by positioning the in security of IoT among the top security threats in 2019 [5]. Thus such security concerns need to be dealt with priority to exploit IoT benefits for global development worldwide.

Cryptography is another word for encryption [6]. Encryption is the process of encoding that hackers cannot read, but may obtain authorizations. Advanced Encryption Standard (AES) is one algorithm that is used in this work [7] and a new proposed steganography algorithm is the core. AES is a symmetric encryption algorithm where both sides use the same key. [8]. AES has a static message block size of 128 bits of text (cipher or plain), and key length 128, 192, or 256 bits. The messages are divided into 128-bit blocks if longer messages are sent. On the other hand, Rivets Shamir Adelman (RSA) is an integral public algorithm used extensively in the corporate and personal communication industries [9]. The benefit of RSA is to provide authentication with customizable key size from 1024 bits to 2048 bits.

The main research is in hiding data through steganography, which means embedding messages within other for the aim of hiding data. It is the art and science of using the digital communication object in such a way that it conceals the existence of secret information [10]. The advantage of steganography is that it can be used without the transmission being detected to transmit classified messages. The generic stenographic embedding and decoding method is clearly described in Figure 1. In this example, a secret message is being embedded inside a cover to produce the stego object [11, 12, 13].

Figure 1 : Generic Process of Encoding and Decoding for Steganography [11]

The first step in embedding and hiding information is the transmission of both the cover message and the secret message into the encoder. One or many protocols are used inside the encoder to embed the secret information in the cover message. The aim of the steganography is not only to prevent others from learning the secret data, but also to eliminate assumption of having concealed information. The message is a secret text which is sent and camouflaged within the carrier to make it more difficult to detect. Second step is the decoding process for the extraction of secret data from a stego object; the stego object is fed into the system. The public or private key to decrypt the original key used within the process of encoding is required to decode the secret information. The secret information embedded within the stego object can be extracted and displayed after the decoding process is completed. Communication mediums/carriers are usually digital files or data, i.e. image, video, text and audio [14, 15, 16]. Various digital mediums use their different features to embed secret data. This paper aims to improve the security in application layer in IoT model (as shown in section 2) based on a new steganography algorithm to get a highly secured IoT application model.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 presents background; section 3 presents the literature review. In section 4, the proposed algorithm is presented, while in Section 5, the performance and security analysis is explained. In section 6, a comparison with others works is demonstrated, and finally, in section 7, we conclude the paper.

II. BACKGROUND

A. IoT Architecture

In IoT systems, the functions and the devices are defined in multiple layers. The numbers of IoT layers are varied according to several opinions. However, according to many researchers [17, 18, 19], The IoT consists mainly of three layers called perception, network and application layers. Each IoT layer has associated security issues. IoT's basic architectural has three layer structures for the devices and technologies; the covering of each layer is shown in figure 2.

- Perception Layer

Perception layer, also known as recognition / sensor layer, obtains the environmental attribute by sensor uses. Also it consists of several sensors such as RFID, infra-red, ZigBee and QR code for collecting surrounding data such as humidity, temperature, power, etc. The function of IoT's devices

cooperation in local and short range networks can also be used in this layer [18].

- Network Layer

The purpose of this layer allows data transmission and routing over the Internet to several IoT hub and devices. In this layer, gateways, switches, Internet and routing devices are used to provide various network services by using some modern technology such as 4G, Wi-Fi, ZigBee, and 3G [19].

- Application Layer

This layer gives the end user the services to fulfill his/her needs. The data availability, confidentiality and authenticity are secured by this layer. In this layer, the main function of IoT is to ensure connectivity between machine, people, and things are achieved [18]. Smart Home, smart cities, smart transport, healthcare and utility services are typical IoT applications.

Figure 2 : The three layers of IoT Architecture [17]

Referring to Section 2, this research focuses on the application layer because it's considered as a top layer of conventional IoT architecture. This layer provides the customized based services according to user relevant needs [18]. This layer's main responsibility is to connect the major gap between the users and applications securely.

B. Security Challenges in IoT Application Layer

The IoT application may be compromised or shut down abruptly as a result of security issues. The malicious attack may be a reason of a virus in the application code which can cause the application to break down. Sometimes applications are unable to provide authenticated services which they are designed to accomplish or even provide inaccurate services. Some main threats for this layer are given as follows:-

- Malevolent code attacks

This kind of attack may be a malicious "worm" that can attack Internet-enabled devices such as home routers security cameras [20]. Moreover, it could get control over steering wheel of autonomous car which results in a serious accident or destroy Wi-Fi of a car.

- Software defenselessness

This type of attack Software vulnerabilities may be increased by non-standard codes written by programmers, the malicious users use this method to obtain their immoral desires

- Phishing attacks

The confidential information can be obtained by attacker via infected email or website by spoofing the participant's verification identity

- Spyware, Worms, and Virus

Attacker may infect the device with malicious software, to steal information, corrupt or denial of service data.

III. LITRATURE REVIEW

In recent years, several researchers have investigated the issue in IoT security vulnerabilities and their solutions. In this section, some of the most relevant researches will be discussed.

Abd El-Latif, A. et.al. [21], described the quantum steganography algorithm with a consideration of the involvement of the quantum computer, hashing and exclusive OR operation (XOR) operations to secure data in fog cloud IoT Technology. It is because in current data communications, in particular both Cloud technologies and IoT technology, the protection of sensitive data is more important. As a result, the choice of protection schemes for these systems therefore needs more time and effort. Their protocol doesn't use quantum states and networking, but only to transmit confidential data and to validate them. To guarantee that their algorithm is protected, hash functions are implemented. Their results showed that the efficiency and protection were reliable, after subjecting their quantum steganography algorithm to the most well-known attacks.

Shah, A., et.al. [22] Implemented lightweight cryptography algorithms. Lightweight cryptography algorithms are the mostly utilized as a part of IoT innovation for more model security with lower memory and power consumption.

Yi, et.al. [23] Acted on protection standard above 80 bits of the rainbow, and the physical analysis was used for the cryptography of Multivariate Quadratic equations (MQ). The outcome of this work reveals that the hidden keys to the rainbow signature could be successfully hacked, thus securing multi-variant signatures on medical systems is significant.

Jan, M.A., et.al. [24] Presented IoT systems mutual authentication. The framework uses the lightweight features of Constrained Application Protocol (CoAP) as an application layer protocol for client-server communication. The AES cypher provides the secure communication channel. Both the Server and the Client challenge each other for mutual authentication by encrypting a 256 bit payload, and then exchanging check-loads. The authentication is achieved during the encounter of request-response without the use of a further layer Datagram Transport Layer Security (DTLS), which improves the cost of communication and computation.

Kothmayr, T et.al. [25] Proposed a two-way IoT authentication protocol. The authentication is handled using the DTLS protocol by exchanging certificates based on RSA.

Qi, M. et.al. [26] Proposed key management and an authentication scheme based on symmetric cryptography and Elliptic curve. The proposed model has resilience to stolen verifier, replay, password guessing, DoS and impersonation attacks in addition to mutual authentication between the user and the Network Control Center (NCC).

Taha, M. S et.al. [27] In order to ensure sensitive message protection during transmission, a combination of a solid steganography and encryption technology was proposed. This approach suggested that the use of the key encryption technique AES-128 be extended before encoding the hidden message in a QR code. Then, the encrypted message in Unicode Transformation Format (UTF-8) format is transformed to a base 64 format to ensure that it is compliant with further processing. Then, another level of security is added to the process by scrambling the encoded image. Finally, the distorted QR code is hidden in an acceptable carrier that is safely transmitted to provide hidden information. The process used was the least significant bit method to obtain digital image steganography.

Demonstration of a comparison between the researches is explained in table1. The comparison consists of two key features that fulfill their patterns to validate the goals of their IoT protection approaches.

TABLE1. COMPARISON WITH OTHER WORKS

	Used Tools	Security algorithms
Abd El-Latif, A. et.al. [21]	The hash function, (XOR), gray code,	steganography in fog cloud IoT
Shah, A., et.al. [22]	-----	cryptography
Yi, et.al. [23]	Sakura-G, Xilinx ISE software, FPGA board	ECC, RSA Cryptography
Jan, M.A, et.al. [24]	-----	CoAP, AES, DTLS protocol
Kothmayr, T et.al. [25]	-----	AES, DTLS protocol
Qi, M. et.al. [26]	-----	key management, Cryptography
Taha, M. S et.al. [27]	QR code	steganography and encryption technology AES-128

In this work, another security solution is proposed using steganography, which is based on some dictionary structure. The next section shows the details of the proposed algorithm.

IV. PROPOSED ALGROTHIM

This section describes the hiding algorithm for securing an application layer in IoT environments. The new proposed steganography algorithm which is composed of four steps: (1) compression. (2) Encryption using AES encryption algorithm. (3) Splitting encrypted text into three bits, (4) Hiding the information by choosing word with number of characters according to the 3 bits where an automated dictionary is required between the sender and the receiver.

A. Hiding Algorithm for Encoding

The proposed algorithm implements the new steganography algorithm. The hiding process takes the secret text message (SM) and generates a cipher paragraph message. While the

embedded message is extracted during the extraction process. The embedding hiding algorithm can be described by the given pseudocode:

Algorithm 1 Embedding hiding Algorithm	
Inputs: secret plain message (SM).	
Output: cipher_new paragraph composed of ordinary paragraph and secret message	
Begin	
Step 1	1. Convert SM to ASCII Code as ASCII-Msg.
	2. Compress ASCII-Msg by using Lempel-Ziv.
Step 2	3. Encrypt compressed ASCII-Msg by using AES-256 as EncMsg.
	4. Convert EncMsg to binary as BinMsg.
	5. Divide BinMsg to 8 bit.
Step 3	6. Loop
	6.1. SHR 1= Shift right the BinMsg 5 bits and convert result to decimal
	6.2. SHR 2 = Shift right BinMsg 2 bits followed by a logical AND operation with binary value of the number seven and convert result to decimal
	6.3. AND 3 = Logical AND operation BinMsg with binary value of the number three and convert result to decimal
	7. End loop
	8. Generate dictionary key array (KD) = adding (SHR 1, SHR 2, AND 3).
Step 4	9. Loop
	9.1. If the word length < the element of KD, hide KD element in word by adding several dots at the word's end equals the difference between the word's length and the KD element .
	9.2. If the word length > the element of KD, hide KD element in word by inserting dash after a number of characters equal to the KD element
	9.3. If the word length = the element of KD, hide KD element in word by adding a comma at the end of the word
	10. End loop
	11. Add semi colons to the end of some unused words in paragraph.
	12. Return cipher_new paragraph composed of ordinary paragraph and secret message.

Experimental 1 for Embedding hiding Algorithm:

1. Secret Message: hello world
2. Convert secret message to ASCII code :
 - 2.1 ASCII code of letter (h) is (104)
 - 2.2 ASCII code of letter (e) is (101)
 - 2.3 ASCII code of letter (l) is (108)

And so on until we get the following ASCII code:
104 101 108 108 111 032 119 111 114 108 100

3. Encrypt using AES & compressed ASCII-Secret Message:

Using Lempel-Ziv compression algorithm and AES encryption algorithm method on the ASCII code resulted from previous step gives us the following compressed encrypted message:

61,246,55,40,96,6,120,203,165,37,121,37,186,86,82,131

4. Convert result to cipher byte array of (8 bit binary) numbers :

Converting number each of the previous numbers in the compressed encrypted message result in the following (8 bit binary) array:

- a. 61 in (8 bit binary) is 00111101
- b. 246 in (8 bit binary) is 11110110 And soon
00111101 11110110 00110111 00101000 01100000
00000110 01111000 11001011 10100101 00100101
01111001 00100101 10111010 01010110 01010010
10000011.

5. For each binary number (8 bit) in the cipher byte array, the three following operations are apply :

- 5.1 Shift right five bits plus one.
- 5.2 Shift right two bits followed by a logical AND operation with binary value of the number seven plus one
- 5.3 Logical AND operation with binary value of the number three plus one.

TABLE 2:
CIPHER BYTE ARRAY ENCRYPTION OPERATION

binary number (8 bit)	SHR 1	SHR 2	AND 3
00111101	00000001	00000111	00000001
Result	1+1 = 2	7 + 1 = 8	1+1 = 2

6. Generate dictionary key array (KD) = adding (SHR 1,SHR 2,AND 3) :

By adding the results of outputs of previous operations (explained in table 2) from the previous step in an array the resulting array is the dictionary key array which is the shared paragraph between sender and receiver
2,8,2,8,6,3,2,6,4,2,3,1,4,1,1,1,2,3,4,7,1,7,3,4,6,2,2,2,2,
2,4,7,2,2,2,2,6,7,3,3,6,3,3,5,3,5,1,4.

7. Hiding the numbers of dictionary key array (KD) in words from the shared paragraph.

I wa-nt to watch... th-e match today... then i..... will sta-rt to make my ho-mework but... before i will make, a. cup of. tea t-o make me refresh and ready to study my lessons I... want t-o w-atc the m-atc today th-en i wil-l start to make my.. homewor-k but before i w-ill make... a cup, of tea. to make me refresh and ready to study my lesson-s I wa-nt to, watch th-e match to-day then i. will start to make, my..... homework but before i. wi-ll make a. cup of, tea to make me refresh and ready to study my.... lessons I..... wan-t to wat-ch the match. today the-n i will start to. make. my homework but bef-ore i.... will m-ake a cup. of tea to make me refresh and ready to study; my lessons; I; want to; watch the; match today; then i will start; to; make my homework but; before; i will; make a; cup of tea to make me refresh and ready to; study my; lessons; I want; to watch; the match; today then i will; start; to make my homework; but; before i; will make; a cup of tea to make me refresh

and ready; to study; my; lessons I; want to; watch the; match today then i; will; start to make my; homework; but before; i will; make a cup of tea to make me refresh and; ready to; study; my lessons; I want; to watch; the match today then; i; will start to make; my; homework but; before i; will make a cup of tea to make me refresh; and ready; to; study my; lessons I; want to; watch the match today; then; i will start to; make; my homework; but before; i will make a cup of tea to make me; refresh and; ready; to study; my lessons;

B. Hiding Algorithm for decoding

Decryption of stego paragraph converts encrypted data to the familiar user format; it is the reverse of encryption process. Throughout the encryption method, the same key (KD) used by the sender must be used over the cipher-text. As shown in following pseudo code, the decryption process is expressed:

Algorithm 2 Decryption Algorithm	
Inputs: cipher new paragraph composed of ordinary paragraph and secret message.	
Output: secret plain message (SM).	
Begin	
Step 4	1. Scan the cipher_paragraph word by word using dictionary
	2. Loop
	2.1. If word contains dots, extract the element of KD by counting word character and dots.
	2.2. If word contains dash, extract the element of KD by counting word character after dash.
	2.3. if word contain comma, Extract the element of KD by counting word character
	3. End loop
	4. Append dictionary key array (KD)
Step 3	5. Convert KD from decimal to binary as BinMsg
	6. Loop
	6.1. SHL 1= Shift left the BinMsg 5 bits.
	6.2. SHL 2 = Shift left BinMsg twice bits.
	6.3. SAME 3 = take BinMsg as it is.
	7. End loop
Step 2	8. Decrypt BinMsg by using AES-256 as DecMsg
Step 1	9. Decompress DecMsg by using Lempel-Ziv as ASCII-Msg
	10. Convert ASCII-Msg by using ASCII Code
	11. Return secret_plain message (SM).
	12. End

Experimental 2 for Decryption Algorithm:

1. Extract the hidden numbers from the shared paragraph where there is one of following three cases:

- 1.1 If the word length is exactly equal to the number required to be hidden in it, the word will be ended by a comma.
- 1.2 If the word length is less than the number required to be hidden in it, the word will have several dots at its end equals the difference between its length and the hidden number.

- 1.3 If the word length is more than the number required to be hidden in it, the word will contain a dash after a number of characters equal to the number required to be hidden in the word.

I wa-nt to watch... th-e match today... then i..... will sta-rt to make my ho-mework but... before i will make, a. cup of. tea t-o make me refresh and ready to study my lessons I... want t-o w-atc h the m-atc h today th-en i wil-l start to make my.. homework-k but before i w-ill make... a cup, of tea. to make me refresh and ready to study my lesson-s I wa-nt to, watch th-e match to-day then i. will start to make, my..... homework but before i. wi-ll make a. cup of, tea to make me refresh and ready to study my.... lessons I..... wan-t to wat-ch the match. today th-e-n i will start to. make. my homework but bef-ore i.... will m-ake a cup. of tea to make me refresh and ready to study; my lessons; I; want to; watch the; match today; then i will start; to; make my homework but;etc.

Hidden numbers = 2,8,2,8,6,3,2,6,4,2,3,1,4,1,1,1,2,3,4,7,1,7,3,4,6,2,2,2,2,4,7,2,2,2,2,6,7,3,3,6,3,3,5,3,5,1,4.

2. KD = hidden numbers – 1

By subtracting one from each number of extracted hidden numbers the result is the following key dictionary array:

Result = 1,7,1,7,5,2,1,5,3,1,2,0,3,0,0,1,2,3,6,0,6,2,3,1,1,1,1,1,3,6,1,1,1,1,5,6,2,2,5,2,2,4,2,4,0,3.

3. Convert KD from decimal to binary :

Convert each of the number in the key dictionary array to its 8-bit binary value to get the following binary array:

a. 1 in 8-bit binary is (00000001)

b. 7 in 8-bit binary is (00001111) and so on

00000001	00001111	00000001	00001111	00001010
00000010	00000001	00001010	00000011	00000001
00000010	00000000	00000011	00000000	00000000
00000000	00000001	00000010	00000011	00001110
00000000	00001110	00000010	00000011	00000001
00000001	00000001	00000001	00000001	00000011
00001110	00000001	00000001	00000001	00000001
00001010	00001110	00000010	00000010	00001010
00000010	00000010	00001000	00000010	00001000
00000000	00000011			

4. For each binary number (8 bit) in the cipher byte array, the three following operations are apply :

- 4.1 The first (8 bit binary value) is shifted left five bits.
- 4.2 The second (8 bit binary value) is shifted left twice bits
- 4.3 The third (8 bit binary value) take it as it is.

TABLE 3:
CIPHER BYTE ARRAY DECRYPTION OPERATION

	SHL 1	SHL 2	SAME 3
binary number (8 bit)	00000001	00001111	00000001
Result	00100000	00011100	00000001
OR (SH1+SH2+SMAE3)	00111101		

❖ **The result is cipher byte array of (8 bit binary) numbers :**

00111101 11110110 00110111 00101000 01100000
00000110 01111000 11001011 10100101 00100101
01111001 00100101 10111010 01010110 01010010
10000011.

5. Convert cipher byte array to decimal :

By converting each number of the cipher byte array to its decimal value:

- a. 00111101 decimal value is 61
- b. 11110110 decimal value is 246

And so on and collect them in an array to get the following decimal array:

61,246,55,40,96,6,120,203,165,37,121,37,186,86,82,
131

6. Decrypt decimal array using AES & decompress to get ASCII code:

For each value in the resulting decimal array from previous step its decompressed using Lempel-Ziv method and decrypted using AES method the result is the ASCII code of the secret message
104 101 108 108 111 032 119 111 114 108 100

7. Convert the ASCII code to secret message:

Converting each element of the ASCII code array to its corresponding character the result is required secret message as shown below

Secret Message: hello world

V. PERFORMANCE AND SECURITY ANALYSIS

In the following section we will be discussing performance and security analysis of the proposed algorithm.

A. Performance Analysis

The performance analysis is measured according to the followings:

1. Embedded Capacity (EC)

The limitation of the input of steganography process is the output from AES-256 which is 128 bits block length. Therefore, the total size of message plus secret message is 0.5 Kbyte which compressed by 25% to be 125 bytes then encrypted to be 1024 bits then using steganography, each three bits need a word to carry its content.

2. Compression

Lossless compression Lempel-Ziv (LZ) [28,29] technique is used as original data can be recovered exactly from the compressed data after a compress/expand cycle, applied for the purpose of reducing required storage space and for reducing the transmission time associated with transfer data from point to point. The proposed algorithm used Lempel-Ziv Lossless compression algorithm that compress the secret

message from 0.5 Kbyte by 25% to be 125 bytes.

3. Time delay

The proposed algorithm time delay to use all the algorithms at sender side is 10 m/s.

The proposed algorithm time delay at the receiver server is 13 m/s.

B. Security Analysis

In this paper, the stego message was embedded in the original cover message. The proposed algorithm has been validated using numerous longitudinal messages and concealed in a shared paragraph. Analyzing the hidden message before and after transmission to the intended receiver reveals that the original cover file has less distortion after secret text is covered.

VI. COMPARISON AND DISCUSSION

Researchers have worked on numerous methods and algorithms in different types of steganography. Researchers have highlighted crucial points for the evaluation of their proposed methods.

Abd El-Latif, A. et.al. [21] Depending on XOR grey code with hash function tools that have been developed based on the IoT Fog Cloud model. Authors also suggested a new IoT protection policy for the industry and created a new protected Fog Cloud IoT Quantum Steganography Algorithm.

Yi, et.al. [23] Based on Sakura-G field-programmable gate array (FPGA) board and Xilinx Integrated Synthesis Environment (Xilinx ISE) software tools for a security of MQ cryptographic algorithm. This algorithm has been described using (RSA) and Elliptic-curve cryptography (ECC) algorithms. The relevance applies to the presentation of a Rainbow physical analysis with a level of protection equal to and greater than 80 bits.

Comparing the new proposed algorithm to existing secure data; there are several points of comparison. There is the technical dimension which compares technologies used in each algorithm that includes:

1. Compression reduces the data to 25% of its original size, which is a vital point in transferring data over network on contrary to other two algorithms which do not compress data before securing.
2. Steganography on the other hand is not commonly used in securing data over network which is considered the main added value in the new proposed algorithm and it gives a new layer of hiding sent data where there is no relation between the secret message and the steganography output.

VII. CONCLUSION

This paper proposes a new algorithm of steganography for secure data in the application layer of the IoT. Through comparison with previous works, the new secure steganography algorithm based on Lempel-Ziv compression, AES cryptography and new steganography algorithm. Performance analysis of the proposed algorithm shows its efficiency while security analysis shows that the attacker is unable to know data in secret message mean while the algorithm is resistant to attacks through encryption and steganography.

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